

SOME ASPECTS OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF USING INDEPENDENT WORKS IN THE FORMATION OF HISTORICAL THINKING

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Abstract. *This article talks about some aspects of the technology of using independent work in the formation of students' historical thinking.*

Keywords: *historical thinking, independent work, education, young generation, teacher, student, methods, social life, social and humanitarian sciences.*

A broad way has been opened to study the centuries-old rich historical, scientific, cultural and religious value and heritage of the Uzbek people, and to use it as a common and priceless property. In the reforms carried out in Uzbekistan, such a process Spiritual and cultural life, education, cultural heritage, historical experience, religious, moral, educational views, lifestyle, colorful relations, science, national holidays, festivals, shows and traditions, art, includes such fields as literature. The specific ethnic characteristics of the people, the nation, and the contribution to the world civilization are actually measured by these spiritual and cultural values.

On January 19, 2021, at the meeting of video selectors dedicated to the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational affairs and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard, the head of our state said, "National history should be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. "We need to teach our youth to learn from history, to draw conclusions, to arm them with historical knowledge and historical thinking" proves how urgent the task is.

History is a precise science that requires accurate knowledge of the chronology of events. It is interconnected with many disciplines. However, unlike them, he considers the development of society as a whole, analyzes the events of social life and their various aspects. The analysis of historical events is based on the "human factor" point of view. That's why "in order to approach history correctly, understand it correctly, and research it correctly, we must join the historical destiny and live in it. That's when we understand its aliveness, its integrity, grasp its entire scope, understand its essence.

The process of searching for the truth of a person's life leads to an interaction with the experience of ancestors, today's reality, life, and the world, and on this basis, he realizes the purpose and meaning of life.

Independent work is an active method of education that solves the educational task assigned by the teacher and under his guidance. Independent work is the organization and implementation of specific activities of students in connection with the set goal. Independent works of students are activities based on their high level of activity, creativity, independent analysis, initiative.

Independent work has several specific features:

the uniqueness of independent work as an active method of education is based on actions that the student performs without the help of the teacher, he chooses the methods of performing these actions himself, improves many actions, controls them in connection with the set goal;

the second characteristic of independent work is reflected in self-control, which is considered a self-directed form of student activity;

the third characteristic is the evaluative activity, which is strongly related to self-control and plays an important role in self-regulation.

And finally, independent work always ends with some kind of result. This is manifested in the form of doing exercises, solving tasks, writing essays, filling in tables, creating graphs, and preparing to answer questions.

Various classifications of independent works are reflected in pedagogical literature. We believe that the classification according to the nature of cognitive activity is more appropriate. Because the rest of the classifications are inextricably linked with the nature of cognitive activity. After all, knowledge is the methodological basis of the educational process, including thinking.

According to the description of cognitive activity, independent work can be divided into three types: recall, knowledge-search, knowledge-practical or creative.

Independent work in the form of recall is aimed at recalling previously acquired knowledge and activating students.

As a result of doing independent work in the form of knowledge-search, students acquire new knowledge.

Cognitive-practical or creative independent work is aimed at expanding the connection of education with practice, and students express their independent thoughts, drawing on the rich concepts and communication methods gathered in their studies and life experiences.

Below we will give examples of interactive methods and examples of their application in practice, which represent a technological approach to the use of independent work in the formation of independent thinking of students.

For example, "Compose a text based on concepts". The method of "composing a text based on concepts" is included in the independent work of the knowledge-research type, and this work requires various logical operations: analysis and generalization, comparison of evidence and events, identification of commonalities and differences in them, separation of primary and secondary characters, reason - reveal the consequences, etc. Usually, students encounter unknown events, new materials, a problem situation arises that requires acquiring new knowledge and finding ways to solve the educational problem. The technology of using this method is as follows:

First, the teacher announces a new topic. After giving a brief description of the topic, he separates the concepts related to the topic and presents it to the students. He shows one of them as an example. Students then use the textbook to independently compose a text based on the concepts.

Using the method of "two-part diaries" also increases the effectiveness of the lesson. For example, "Diaries in Two Parts" allows readers to connect the content of the text with their own personal experience, to satisfy their natural curiosity. Two-part diaries are especially useful when students are assigned to read a large text at home outside of the classroom.

For a two-part journal, students should draw a vertical line down the middle of the blank paper and divide it in half. On the left side of the paper, they write down which part of the text made the most impression on them. Perhaps it will evoke some kind of memory or recall events that happened in their lives, or just surprise. Or it arouses a strong feeling of dissatisfaction in their

hearts. On the right, they should comment: What made them write this particular quote? What thoughts did they have? What question did they have in this regard? In short, while reading the text, students should stop from time to time and make such marks in their double diaries.

Let's focus on the "Most Important Terms" method.

This method directs students to independent work. For this, the teacher selects several concepts of a new topic and presents them to the students. Students, with the help of the teacher, independently write comments on each of these concepts. Then the teacher explains the topic based on these concepts. Students compare what is said with what they have written. They solve controversial concepts together.

The possibility of using this method in history lessons is high, and it serves to activate students' cognitive activity. For example, in the lesson "History of Uzbekistan" of the 7th grade, the teacher presents the following concepts to the students on the topic "Land-property relations in the 9th-10th centuries":

- 1) Sultanate property;
- 2) the property is unique;
- 3) property lands;
- 4) foundation lands;
- 5) iqto lands;
- 6) communal lands.

So, in conclusion, thinking means the ability to know through concepts as a higher form of reflection of the processes of existence in a person by summarizing the nature of the interaction and connection of things and events. Historical thinking is the ability to know historical events and phenomena, to understand historical processes by summarizing the essence of the mutual relationship and connection between historical events and events, and to create a cause-and-effect relationship between them.

Historical thinking is an important criterion that determines a person's ability to analyze historical events, evaluate them, and understand their significance. Among the social and humanitarian sciences, history occupies a special place in the formation of historical thinking in general education school students. Because this science, which encompasses the whole life of a person in its entirety, creates ample opportunities for him to develop himself in all aspects, to think independently, to understand the essence of life by creating historical consciousness and historical memory.

REFERENCES

1. Мирзиёев Ш.М. “Миллий тараққиёт йўлимизни қатъият билан давом эттириб янги босқичга кўтарамиз”. Т., 2017.
2. Ахмедов В. “Тарихдан сабоқлар”. Т., “Ўқитувчи”, 1994.
3. Ўзбекистоннинг янги тарихи. Ўзбекистон мустақиллик йилларида. 3-китоб. Шарқ. Т., 2000.
4. Зайнитдинова М. Ўқувчиларнинг мустақил фикрлаш фаолиятларини ривожлантириш омиллари // ж. Халқ таълими. – 2004. - №1. – Б. 132-135.
5. Мусаев Ж. Мустақил фикрлаш салоҳиятини ривожлантириш машқлари. //ж. Халқ таълими– 2007. - №1. – Б. 7-13.

6. Жабборов Й. Ўрта Осиёда ижтимоий-фалсафий фикрлар тарихи. Т., Шарқ 1997 й. 176 б.
7. Kadyrov U.D., Kadyrov G.U. DRUG ADDICTION AS A SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM. Science and innovation international scientific journal. Volume 3 | March, 2024.
8. Қодиров, У. (2023). Психологик хизмат – замонавий таълим тизимининг ажралмас таркибий қисми. Современные тенденции психологической службы в системе образования: теория и практика, 1(1), 21–24. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/psychological-service-education/article/view/23460>
9. Ишмухамедов Р.Ж., Юлдашев М. Таълим ва тарбияда инновацион педагогик технологиялар. – Тошкент: Нихол, 2013.
10. Сагдиев А., Фузаилова Г., Ҳасанова М. Тарих ўқитиш методикаси. – Тошкент: ТДПУ, 2008.